

A visual framework for software requirements traceability

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ABSTRACT

Requirement traceability supports several activities of software development processes such as impact analysis, requirement changes, maintenance, verification, and validation of a software system. For its effective use in those activities, the graphical representation of traceability data plays an important role. However, several traceability tools lack an excellent visual representation to present these type of data. Therefore, this paper presents a visual framework which has been designed and proposed as a prototype tool that can visualize traceability data. The framework applies data visualization techniques to represent requirements and its artefacts relationships as colour-coded symbols on a node-link diagram; users can traverse the graph with an impact analysis method to understand data and make decisions. The evaluation result shows that the proposed tool is useful and easy enough in terms of improving user interaction and to better understand requirement traceability data.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Requirement traceability is the process of identifying and following the life of requirements in forwards or backwards direction created during a software development lifecycle [1]. Visualization is an important technique used to represent traceability relationships between requirements and artefacts to support various software development activities such as impact analysis, requirement changes, validation of the system, maintenance, and software evolution [2]. During software development, a large number of complex traceability relationships are generated [3]. Several traceability tools lack excellent visual representation to trace relationships between requirements and artefacts [4]. Therefore, there is a need to have a graphical visual tool that can help to visualize and represent traceability relationships between requirements and artefacts [5]. With the help of visualization techniques and graphical notations, the user can easily visualize tracing the relationships between requirements and artefacts [6]-[8].

In this paper, we proposed a visual framework in order to visualize the traceability relationships between requirements and its artefacts during the software development process or requirement change. We adopt the graphical user interface design for visual information-seeking mantra, “overview first, zoom and filter, then details-on-demand”, as proposed by Schneiderman [9]. The tool uses graphical notations to represent the traceability of requirements and artefacts relationships bi-directionally. Users can traverse the graph for impact analysis and reduce visual clutter to understand their data quickly and make data visualization has been recognized as a significant research field focused on the application of visualization techniques to help people understand and analyze traceability data [10]. Visualization techniques, design principles, human perception, and colour theory are applied in data presentation [9]. Traceability techniques

such as graphs, matrix, and hyperlinks are used to show complex data [11]. A graph-based visualization is the most common visualization technique used by traceability systems [12], [13]. It supports the visualization of an overview of traceability links between multiple requirements and artefacts as nodes, with relationships as edges. Li and Maalej [7] recently examined and compared graphs, matrix, lists, and hyperlinks techniques in an empirical study to show which of these visualization techniques are more suitable to be conducted in any given context. The study highlights the traceability graph as the best to support management tasks. Several visualization tools were developed to visualize the traceability relationships between requirements and artefacts as a node-link diagram representation on a network graph [14]-[17].

Rubasinghe *et al.* [5] proposed a traceability support visualization tool for heterogeneous artefacts in DevOps environments. The tool eliminates and updates conflicts raised among artefacts, while the developed artefacts in the project are outdated. They proposed traceability process model consists of artefact change detection, change impact analysis, and change propagation. Moreover, this tool provides multi-user accessibility and is integrated with a prominent DevOps tool stack to enable collaborations. Whenever the number of artefacts increased, the graph complexity of viewing the relationships also increased. However, with the predefined overcrowded relationships in the graph view, the graph complexity was reduced to provide an effective analysis vision. In contrast, visualization of the links may provide the release of each software product. Figure 1 shows an example of an interactive traceability graph, where nodes denote the artefact and edges show the links.

Figure 1. An example of the change propagated for interactive traceability graph [5]

Similarly, another study by Beier and Muller [3] presents a prototype visualization tool for traceability artefacts called "Ariadne's eye". It is an interactive method of scaling, zooming, and folding in (node-link) of a vertical tree and balloon tree layouts. The tool is visualized to compare three geometrical forms, namely circle, eclipse, and polygon, that help users understand and select a type of hierarchical framework to link all elements and their direct ancestral line easily. The systematic visualization layout for complex graphs consists of numerous hierarchical artefacts. The spatially separates the hierarchical artefacts and traces the relationships to make it readable and understandable to the users on the graph, as shown in Figure 2. The study is limited and valid with two issues; the moderately low number of participants and the number of elements within an artefact far away from the industrial artefacts. They further refined and advanced the layout according to user feedback. They implemented their final ideas as an interactive visualization tool called Ariadne's eye. The result analysis method is displayed where the mean values per task and layout are given.

Figure 2. Ariadne's eye visualization tool [3]

2. PROPOSED METHOD

This research study developed a visual framework design to help users visualize requirement traceability data. The visual framework follows the design of advanced graphical user interface (GUI) guide for visual information seeking mantra, “overview first, zoom and filter, then details on-demand”, which was proposed by Schneiderman in 1996. The regular use of the mantra is an indication that shows the excellent design and helps many practitioners in different design scenarios [18]. In Figure 3, the overview of the proposed visual framework is presented.

Figure 3. The proposed visual framework

In Figure 3, it can be observed that the visual framework provides data input, visualization approaches, and implementation of the prototype tool called VizTraceArtefacts. The use of visualization techniques helps to display the overview of traceability data and enables the user to modify the detailed information displayed. The selected visual cluster can be filtered to reduce the number of visual clutters for requirements and artefacts relationships on the network graph.

Moreover, the tool enables the analysis of understanding traceability data in a different view. Figure 4 shows some typical shapes and colours used to represent demographic appearances of requirements, artefacts, relationships, and directions. The colour-coded shapes represent requirements and artefacts using cycles, while the colour-coded arrows represent relationships and directions, all depending on the type of colour used.

Figure 4. Example of the types of color-coded symbols used

The implemented prototype tool was made through the application of an adopted novel methodological guide for visual information seeking mantra [18]. The methodology is presented and categorized into three (3) phases that include preliminary study and analysis, designing the framework and its implementation, and evaluation. The selection of visualization techniques to implement the tool follows the design of advanced GUI guide for visual information seeking mantra, “overview first, zoom and filter, then details on-demand”, as proposed by Schneiderman in 1996. The frequent use of the mantra is evidence in which many practitioners find it helpful in different design scenarios [18], [19].

The first technique applied is called an “overview first”; it is a perspective method of an understanding dataset with a complete diagram structure familiar with data designs [20]. This technique represents the overview of data as a node-link diagram to improve user understandability and communication [21]. “Node-link diagram” is a type of visualization on a graph that shows relationships and represents their connections as nodes and edges to identify the type of relationships that exist between a group of entities [22]. Figure 5 shows an overview of our traceability visualization from VizTraceArtefacts. The nodes represent requirements and artefacts; the links represent relationships and show directions of forward and backward. All the links are coloured based on the type in order to identify them on the network.

Figure 5. Overview of node-link visualization showing requirements and artefacts relationships

The second technique applied is “zoom and filter” which is suitable and meant for an overview as node-link representation on the network. “Both the techniques help to reduce visual clutter from view and

represent data easily on the network” [18]. The “zoom” technique is a process of fine-tuning to adjust components of data position and size on the screen, while “filter” is considered as alteration and navigation to represent an essential viewpoint on the diagram [23]. “Zooming and filtering” allow users to filter nodes based on their needs because many visualized components are limited, therefore the perceptual clarity of users needs an improvement. Figure 6 shows the VizTraceArtefacts zoom and filter traceability visualization.

Figure 6. Zoom and filter visualization showing relationships between a requirement and artefacts

The last technique applied is “details-on-demand” to offer more information without altering the design view. Therefore, the “ordered-lists” method is used to enable a user to find outliers on the network. Accordingly, “ranking” is a general approach to organize or disorganize a set of items by calculating the rank of an individual item according to the value of one to many of its attributes [24]. This approach enables a user to combine the attribute ranking and partition, ordered-lists and colour-coding to measure the scale of nodes and edges on the network. Furthermore, it also assists in the evaluation of nodes performance that has relation with one another and prioritizes them according to the ranking. Table 1 shows the ordered list for comparing rankings.

Table 1. Ordered list for comparing rankings

Rank	Node (artefacts)	Relationship type
4.00	Requirements (REQ)	Is tested by
3.00	Use case (UC)	Depends on
3.00	Source code (SC)	Is verified on
2.00	Test case (TC)	Influenced
2.00		Is implemented by
1.00		Lead to creation of
1.00		Is modified by
1.00		Is satisfied by

We used colour-coded circles for each type of node to support usability aspects in the establishment of traceability artefacts and relationships. We considered the requirement-use case, use case-source code, source code-test case requirement-test case, and use case-test case artefacts. However, the design was altered to directly reflect in artefacts; consequently, the nodes represent requirements and artefacts while the edges show the traceability relationships and directions. As shown in Figure 5, the nodes in blue represent requirements, the green nodes represent use cases, the red nodes represent source codes, and the light blue nodes represent test cases. The colour arrows represent links that show the relationships with directions between requirements and artefacts. ForceAtlas2 layout algorithm is used to position whole nodes on the network. It is a “spring analogue method of drawing graphs to position nodes and links that are iteratively refined and present them until the whole energy of the system is minimized” [25]. Therefore, “node-link diagrams significantly leave an empty background space and come across scalability issues when applied to larger graphs” [22]. The ranking method used to measure the number of connected nodes is the “degree” between requirements and artefacts. Each node is ranked based on the method of an ordered list, and a partition is allocated to a range of colour groups. The users can traverse the graph for impact analysis to further understand the data and make decisions.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this study show that the proposed tool is found to be very useful and easy in terms of visualizing requirement traceability data by all respondents. The study findings on usefulness of this framework show that it is effective in helping users to improve their understanding and make decisions. Whenever the complexity of artefacts relationships increases, visualization gives users an impression to visualize, trace and filter artefacts to discover information easily. The result is not statistically significant as the case study has a small number of participants. Therefore, there is only a minor difference between participants in terms of speed and time taken to complete the assessment.

According to the bar chart, all recorded items have the highest number of mean scores that is between "4 to 5". All the respondents have assured that the proposed tool make their job easier and they clearly understand traceability data better. The use of zoom and filter techniques help display the necessary information and reduced visual clutter that increased the effectiveness of the tool (mean of 4.76). Some respondents acknowledged the tool as it reduces searching effort and clicks features, which makes work very useful and more comfortable (mean of 4.16) for simplifying their work. As a result of increasing job performance (mean of 4.37) and reduction of time taken to complete a task, this enables them to perform their job easier (mean of 4.0). Moreover, the increase in productivity items is slight as an opinion made by a single respondent (mean of 4.3) due to task complexity and confusion at the time to join more than one visualization technique. Figure 8(a) shows the score mean of usefulness and Figure 8(b) shows the score for ease of use between all metrics.

The result of ease of use shows that the proposed tool is easy and turns out to be skillful, clear, and understandable as all respondents answered all the questions appropriately. In the recorded items, clear and understandable (mean of 4.8), skillful (mean of 4.6), remember (mean of 4.0), easy to learn, and easy to use (mean of 4.3) achieved the highest score mean for ease of use factors. On the other hand, controllable achieved the lowest mean score of (3.5) as a small number of respondents confirmed that they faced problems in navigating to each visualization technique to help them perform their tasks. Thus, in the case of a first-time user, it is impossible to learn something new quickly in a short time. Due to this issue, a manual with some guidelines from the researcher was provided to simplify respondents' learning process. Moreover, an open-ended evaluation result shows a perfect meaningful answer from the respondents' understanding after using the proposed tool which inspired this discussion towards the use of an open-ended question. The respondents were all satisfied with how each visualization technique applied to the visual framework helps them improve their understanding and complete the assessment tasks.

(a)

(b)

Figure 8. The mean score of (a) usefulness and (b) ease of use

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a visual framework and a visualization tool called VizTraceArtefacts that supports the visualization of software requirement traceability data. The tool applies data visualization techniques to represent requirements traceability data as colour-coded symbols on a node-link diagram. The main contribution of this framework is that it can help users to improve their understanding and interaction, develop products rapidly, increase software quality, reduce maintenance effort, and manage requirement change frequently during the software development lifecycle. The evaluation result obtained from usability measures in the considered case study shows that the visual framework is significant enough in terms of improving user interaction and understanding. The tool can be further enhanced with a filtering search mechanism technique due to the efficiency benefits to search for requirements using keywords and limit the search filter to only specific relationships, directions, link number, and properties.

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